

SYNTHESIS OF *TRANS-ANTI-TRANS*-9-KETO-PERHYDRO PHENANTHRENE*

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A general method has been described for the synthesis of perhydrophenanthrene.

With the elucidation of the structures of sterols and bile acids, the chemistry of perhydrophenanthrene has gained singular importance. Recently Linstead *et al* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 842, 850; *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1991) have initiated a thorough investigation of the stereochemical problem that arises out of the four asymmetric carbon atoms in the perhydrophenanthrene molecule and in this connection they have prepared all the possible stereochemically homogeneous perhydrodiphenic acids and have used them as reference compounds for the determination of configurations of different perhydrophenanthrenes. For the preparation of the three stereochemically homogeneous perhydrophenanthrene derivatives, whose configurations have been settled, the above authors have employed the method of catalytic hydrogenation of aromatic and partially aromatic phenanthrenes and also that of 9-keto- $\Delta^{10:11}$ -dodecahydrophenanthrene obtained by the method of Rapson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1285). It is interesting to note that the 9-keto-perhydrophenanthrene, obtained by the last method, has been shown, by its oxidation to one of the diphenic acids, to possess the *trans-anti-trans* configuration which is identical with the configuration assigned to the rings A, B, and C of the cholestane system occurring in nature. The above methods, however, have so far not found their application for the preparation of the perhydrophenanthrene derivatives with the angular methyl groups.

Quite recently, Robinson *et al* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 386; 1943, 491) have succeeded in synthesising 9-keto- $\Delta^{9:14}$ -13-methyl-dodecahydrophenanthrene and an isomer of androsteredione. But the method of Manich's base condensation (DuFau, McQuillin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53), which has been utilised for the preparation of the above substances, generally gives rise to the *cis* configuration of the fused carbon rings (Linstead, Millidge and Walpole, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1140).

The present paper describes a method for the building up of perhydrophenanthrene nucleus which offers the possibility of application in the synthesis of *cyclopentanoperhydrophenanthrene* with angular methyl groups.

For the preparation of 2-(2'-carbethoxy-cyclohexyl)-cyclohexanone derivatives which have been utilised as the starting materials a method similar to that of Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 27, 453) and Banerjee and Roy (*Science & Culture*, 1944-1945, 10, 134) has been successfully employed. Attempts to prepare the same starting material by the Michael condensation between ethyl cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate and cyclohexanone or ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (Rapson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1626) proved to be futile. Ethyl cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate, prepared from *cyclo-*

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hexanone cyanohydrin in the usual way, has been allowed to react with ethyl sodiocyanoacetate. The potassium derivative of (I) is condensed with ethyl 5-iodovalerate (Banerjee and Roy, *loc. cit.*) to yield (II, R=CN). The optimum yield is obtained when the temperature of the reaction mixture is allowed to rise to the boiling point in course of several hours (*cf.* Mitter and Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 69). The condensation product is hydrolysed and esterified to furnish (II, R=H) which on treatment with sodium dust gives (III, R=CO₂Et). The Dieckmann product gives positive ferric reaction and can not be distilled without decomposition. It is hydrolysed and esterified to yield (III, R=H) which is reacted with activated zinc and ethyl bromoacetate. The hydroxy diester (IV, R=OH; R₁=R₂=C₂H₅) is dehydrated in ethereal solution with thionyl chloride and pyridine to the corresponding unsaturated ester (V, R=C₂H₅) which on hydrolysis furnishes a solid dicarboxylic acid (V, R=H). The unsaturated acid on hydrogenation yields a solid saturated dicarboxylic acid (IV, R=R₁=R₂=H) which is esterified with diazomethane. The diester (IV, R=H; R₁=R₂=CH₃), thus obtained, has been cyclised to yield 9-keto-10-carbomethoxy-perhydrophenanthrene in excellent yield. 9-Keto-perhydrophenanthrene (VI) is obtained in the liquid state by hydrolysis of the above β-ketonic ester in the usual manner. The above ketone has been converted into its oxime and after several crystallisation from ethanol melts at 226-27° (lit. 227-28°; Linstead and Walpole, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 842). The ketone is regenerated from its oxime and after purification by distillation solidifies, m.p. 46-47.5° (lit. 49°; Linstead and Walpole, *loc. cit.*). A portion of the above liquid ketone (VII) is oxidised with a mixture of concentrated and fuming nitric acids to furnish a perhydrodiphenic acid, m.p. 240-41° (lit. 237-40° and 246-47°, Linstead and Doering, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1991; 243-44°, Linstead and Walpole, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 850).

The above experimental evidences show that the synthetical 9-keto-perhydrophenanthrene obtained by the method detailed above possesses *trans-anti-trans* stereochemical configuration represented by (VI). Here the stereochemical configuration of the four asymmetric carbon atoms C₁₁, C₁₂, C₁₃ and C₁₄ in the synthetical specimen is also identical with that of cholane system occurring in nature.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

*cyclo*Hexanone cyanohydrin was prepared according to the method of Clemo and Welch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2629). When the temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained between 2° and 5° by external cooling the yield was quantitative.

Ethyl cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate.—The above cyanohydrin (210 g.) in pyridine (272 g.) was cooled in a freezing mixture and dehydrated with thionyl chloride (130 c.c.). The reaction product was worked up in the usual way, yield 167 g.

The unsaturated nitrile was hydrolysed with aqueous caustic potash according to the method of Linstead and Boorman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 258).

The unsaturated acid (127 g.) was esterified by refluxing with alcohol (50 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (5 c.c., *d*, 1'84) for 24 hours, yield 135 g. The ester could be directly obtained from the nitrile (136 g.) by refluxing with a mixture of rectified spirit (25 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (43 c.c.) for 36 hours, yield 13 g.

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-cyclohexyl-1-cyanoacetate (I).—A mixture of the above unsaturated ester (181 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (168 c.c.) was added to sodium ethoxide (prepared from 30.2 g. of sodium) in alcohol (370 c.c.). The reaction mixture was heated on the water-bath for 30 hours, diluted with iced dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and distilled, yield 228 g.

Ethyl 5-Bromovalerate.—Allyl iodide was prepared according to Dutta (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 1005).

(a) Allyl iodide (34 g.) was added to magnesio malonic ester (Mg. 2.4 g.; malonic ester, 32 g.; alcohol, 34 c.c. and carbon tetrachloride, 1 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 12 hours and worked up as usual, yield 18 g. (Lund, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 935).

(b) Allyl iodide (40 g.) was added to sodiomalonic ester (prepared from sodium 5.5 g.; malonic ester, 56 c.c. and alcohol, 55 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 12 hours. The yield was quantitative. The use of benzene as solvent in the above condensation furnished a quantitative yield of the product.

5-Bromovaleric acid (50 g.), obtained from allyl malonate, following the method of Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 575) was esterified with alcohol (150 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (9 c.c.) by refluxing for 24 hours, yield 50 g.

Diethyl 2-Cyano-2 (2'-carbethoxy-cyclohexyl)-pimelate.—Ethyl 5-iodovalerate (56 g.) was added to the potassio derivative of the above cyanoacetic ester (I), prepared from

potassium (9 g.), cyanoester (70 g.) and xylene (150 c.c.). The reaction mixture was left overnight, heated on the water-bath for 12 hours, at 110° for another 12 hours and finally refluxed in an oil-bath for 12 hours. It was washed thrice with water, dried and distilled, b. p. 179-82°/0.4 mm., yield 56 g.

The use of bromo ester in the above condensation also yielded the final product (56 g.). But the use of a mixture of xylene and alcohol as solvent furnished a rather poorer yield of the final product. (Found : C, 63.9 ; H, 8.5. $C_{21}H_{28}O_8N$ requires C, 63.79 ; H, 8.35 per cent).

Diethyl 2-(2'-carbethoxy-cyclohexyl)-pimelate.—The above substituted cyano ester (56 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (140 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (100 c.c.) and water (140 c.c.) for 36 hours. It was next diluted with water and the precipitated acid was extracted with ether. The crude acid was esterified with alcohol (200 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (28 c.c.) by refluxing for 40 hours. The ester was worked up and distilled, b. p. 190°/4 mm., yield 42 g. (Found : C, 66.98 ; H, 9.44. $C_{20}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 64.87 ; H, 9.18 per cent).

2-(2'-Carbethoxy-cyclohexyl)-cyclohexanone.—The above pimelate (33 g.) was refluxed with sodium dust (4 g.) in benzene (160 c.c.) until the whole of sodium had reacted. The reaction mixture was decomposed with iced dilute sulphuric acid and the precipitated β -ketonic ester was extracted with ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The ether-benzene layer was dried and distilled, but the β -ketonic ester could not be distilled without decomposition. The alkaline washing was acidified and the precipitated oil after extraction with ether was mixed with the neutral β -ketonic ester. The β -ketonic ester gave a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The crude product was hydrolysed by refluxing it with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.) for 30 hours. The acid together with water were removed under reduced pressure and the residue, thus obtained, was esterified with alcohol (100 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) by refluxing for 24 hours. The resulting ester was worked up and distilled, b. p. 151°/4.5 mm. (Found : C, 71.3 ; H, 9.42. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 71.42 ; H, 9.52 per cent).

The oxime was prepared by refluxing the keto-ester (0.5 g.) with an excess of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, pyridine and alcohol. It was obtained in silky needles, m.p. 138-40°. (Found : C, 67.72 ; H, 9.44. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2N$ requires C, 67.41 ; H, 9.4 per cent).

Attempts for the preparation of (III, R=H).—(a) A solution of ethyl cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate (16 g.) in alcohol (16 c.c.) was added to a solution of potassium ethoxide (potassium 1 g., ether 10 c.c., and alcohol 33 c.c.) cooled in freezing mixture and then it was left for several days. No reaction took place.

(b) A mixture of ethyl potassium cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (metal, 3.9 g., β -keto-ester, 17 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) and pyridine (20 c.c.) and cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate (10.7 g.) was refluxed for 40 hours. But no reaction took place.

(c) A solution of ethyl cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate (15.8 g.) in ether (30 c.c.) was added to a boiling ethereal mixture of sodiocyclohexanone prepared from sodamide (4 g.), cyclohexanone (9.8 g.) and ether (150 c.c.). It was refluxed for 8 hours and on working up as usual no product could be isolated.

Ethyl (2'-carbethoxy-cyclohexyl)-cyclohex-1-ene-2-acetate.—The above keto-ester

(III, R=H, 17 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of thiophene-free benzene (150 c.c.), zinc (5 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (8 c.c.) and a crystal of iodine for 2 hours. Next a lot of zinc (2 g.), a crystal of iodine and ethyl bromoacetate (4 c.c.) were added and the mixture refluxed for 1 hour. Another lot of zinc (2 g.) and a crystal of iodine were added and the heating continued for another 2 hours. The product was decomposed with iced dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with benzene, washed with dilute ammonia and water, b. p. 140-50°/0.4 mm.

The above hydroxy compound in a mixture of ether (100 c.c.) and pyridine (20 c.c.) was dehydrated with thionyl chloride (10 c.c.). The reaction mixture was left overnight and decomposed with iced dilute acid and worked up in the usual way, b. p. 180°/4 mm., yield 5.8 g. (Found : C, 70.72 ; H, 9.22. $C_{14}H_{20}O$ requires C, 70.8 ; H, 9.31 per cent).

1-(2'-Carboxy-cyclohexyl)-cyclohex-1-ene-2-acetic Acid.—The above unsaturated compound (5 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing it with methanolic caustic potash (5 g. in 50 c.c.) for 2 hours and then for another 7 hours with aqueous potash (5 g. in 5 c.c.). The methanol was removed and the dilute solution was extracted with ether. After alkaline solution was acidified with acetic acid and then extracted with ether. After removal of ether the residue was boiled with acetic acid, charcoaled and filtered. The unsaturated dibasic acid was next crystallised from methanol. It began to melt with decomposition at 195°, almost clear at 200° and perfectly clear at 205°, yield 3 g. (Found : C, 68.00 ; H, 8.4. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 67.67 ; H, 8.27 per cent).

2'-Carboxyl-dicyclohexyl-2-acetic Acid.—The above unsaturated acid (2.8 g.) was hydrogenated in acetic acid solution over Adam's catalyst (0.3 g.). It was crystallised from benzene, m. p. 188-89°. (Found : C, 67.45 ; H, 9.15. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 67.16 ; H, 8.95 per cent).

Methyl 2'-carboxymethoxyl-dicyclohexyl-2-acetate—An ethereal solution of diazomethane was added to the above acid (2.8 g.) in ether (200 c.c.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 2 days. The excess of diazomethane was destroyed with acetic acid and the ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and distilled, b. p. 153°/3 mm., yield 2.8 g. (Found : C, 68.89 ; H, 9.35. $C_{17}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 68.9 ; H, 9.45 per cent).

9-Keto-perhydrophenanthrene.—The above ester (2.8 g.) was refluxed with benzene (40 c.c.) and sodium dust (0.46 g.) for 6 hours when all the sodium went into solution. It was worked up as mentioned before. The β -keto-ester gave a light violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and was hydrolysed, as mentioned before, and distilled, b. p. 133°/4.5 mm, yield 1.2 g.

A mixture of the above ketone (0.4 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.6 g.), pyridine (1 c.c.) and alcohol (2.5 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours. After diluting the reaction mixture the oxime was crystallised from large amount of ethanol in milk-white silky needles, m. p. 226-27°. (Found : C, 76.2 ; H, 10.48. $C_{14}H_{20}ON$ requires C, 76.01 ; H, 10.4 per cent).

The above oxime (0.25 g.) was refluxed with 5% sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) for 6 hours. The solution was extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried and distilled. The distillate solidified with an adhering oil which was removed on a porous plate, m. p. 46-47.5°.

Perhydrodiphenic-1:1'-dicarboxylic Acid.—The above 9-keto-perhydrophenanthrene (0.7 g.) was treated with a mixture of concentrated and fuming nitric acids (1:3 ; 3.2 c.c.) and the mixture was heated on the steam-bath for 45 minutes. On cooling and diluting the reaction mixture with water a solid with some tar separated out. It was thrice crystallised from dilute acetic acid in needles, m.p. 240-41°. (Found : C, 66.36 ; H, 8.7. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 66.19 ; H, 8.66 per cent).

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